

TO BE ABLE TO CHOOSE THE RIGHT METHODS OF LANDSCAPING SCHOOL AND PRESCHOOL AREAS

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Annotation Landscaping of schools and preschools using modern landscape techniques. In landscape architecture, three types of landscaping methods have been adopted in the creation of green areas: regular, landscape, and mixed methods, with a focus on the correct choice of one of these methods.

Keywords: alleys, compositions, lawns, sheds, playgrounds, elegant, landscaping, shrubs, pine-leaf, forms.

INTRODUCTION In the process of landscaping the areas of schools and preschools, it will be necessary to bring the staff to the artistic charm in the form of an elegant landscape in the eyes of visitors. To do this, you need to know the general principles of the green area. These principles are: the order in which the land should be planned, ie the style, the arrangement of plant species, the appearance of a wave of flowers in them, the glow of living and inanimate objects in the human eye, the center of the composition of green areas, their proportions and scale, shade and the interrelationship of light, as well as the duration of the flowering period of the plant world, the elegant compositional composition of deciduous and coniferous trees and shrubs, the composition of herbaceous plants and flowers, the composition of lawns, the harmonious composition of architectural buildings and structures. Landscaping methods adapted to the landscape around the school and preschool areas, the flowering period of the trees, all of which must and must be taken into account. Three types of landscaping methods have been adopted in the creation of green areas: regular, landscape, and mixed methods.

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MAIN PART In a regular style - all landscaping elements and objects will have a regular or correct geometric shape. The flowerbeds that are formed are circular, rectangular, rhombic, triangular, heart-shaped, etc. ; the corridors to be constructed will be in the form of a straight line or a semicircle. The planting schemes of ornamental trees, shrubs and flowers are strictly defined when included in the plan. According to the planting scheme, ornamental trees, shrubs and flowering plants of the same species and the same size are selected. Most importantly, in landscaping, it is taken into account that the plant world alternately exhibits a wave of flowers. If the color of one of the flowers complements or complements the other, it is well received by the human eye (green with red, air color with orange). The reds, oranges, and yellows are warm, bright, and look good from a distance; green, air color, and purple remain cold, dull, and somewhat abstract at a distance, absorbing the surrounding background. White is compatible with all other colors. Silver and gray are the centered colors of the plants. The set of colors in plants can be in the following order:

1. Contrast is the placement of contrasting colors. Red-green, air-orange, yellow-purple.

2. Harmonic - colors are placed alternately. Red-yellow, orange-green, yellow-blue, green-air color.

3. Disharmonic - the colors are arranged with other adjacent colors: red-orange, yellow-green, blue air color-purple.

4. Nuance - from light color to dark color of the same color; lasts from light red to dark red, the air from dark blue to dark blue. Landscaping in the style of landscaping differs in the division of the area into different areas: the division into areas of the same asymmetry, the free planting of trees, shrubs and flowers, the creation of pools of some kind of view from the human point of view. The elements of the landscape-style area are placed symmetrically. Kindergarten area in the greening of the preschool organization is a place for a child to spend part of the day. He is a child The second is the house, so the exterior as its inner part The exterior should also be comfortable and beautified. The territory of the kindergarten is safe for children, to serve for their good rest and proper development should. To do this, first of all, the landscape of the territory is correct must be established. On the territory of kindergartens must have the following elements: - - green areas; - - alleys and sidewalks; - - pavilion, (gazebo) sheds; - - stadiums and

sports grounds. Landscape design of a preschool organization should be the basis of primary botanical education for the child. In addition to local trees, shrubs and flowers, it is recommended to plant rare exotic plants here. Conifers are air purifiers and healers, but it is best to plant them away from play areas, such as in front of a gate or in the central part of an entrance. On New Year's Eve, the roadside Christmas trees are decorated, giving the children a festive mood from the entrance. Deciduous trees are planted along the wall, or along the alley. It is advisable to plant one or more tall, broad spreading trees to provide shade for the playgrounds. Shrub and green living walls serve well in kindergarten landscape design in dividing groups between groups and the territory in general. Legistrum separates the living wall corridors planted with samshit and camel from the squares to separate the beresklets from the playgrounds. The territory of the kindergarten must have flower beds, flower beds and mixboards. For them it is necessary to choose different and brightly colored flowers. Flowerbeds should delight the eyes of children from early spring to late autumn. It is advisable to plant annual thornless flowers - calendula, lily of the valley, chamomile, carnations, petunias near places where children play. You can decorate the ground floor or central entrance part flower garden with unique plants. The organization of flower gardens, which children take care of, also plays an important role in the formation of the child's personality. It consists of small plots of land that should be accessible to the child from all sides. In the mixed landscaping method, regular and landscaping methods are used together. This includes buildings and structures with an architectural landscape in the human eye; gates of various types at the entrances to schools, preschool educational institutions; fountains that take on a certain look, as well as flowerbeds that have a certain geometric look, are depicted with a whole plant world. It is also planned to create green areas in landscaping (England) style, in addition to the regular classical style in landscaping. When creating green areas in the landscape style, it is necessary to preserve the natural landscape, including various types of landscaping work. To do this, we experts must pay attention to the scenic and biological properties of the plant world. It will also be necessary to adapt the flora to the architectural landscape appearance of buildings and structures and to place them correctly.

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